

Linguacultural Features of Phraseological Units in Italian Language

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Abstract:

Linguoculturology is an actively developing field of linguistics. Linguoculturology is a new branch of science, which deals with manifestations of culture of different nations, which became fixed and are reflected in the language. Linguoculturology is a rapidly expanding field at the interface between linguistics, cultural studies, ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics. However, it has its own integral aspect of studying language and culture.

This paper is dedicated to the analysis of linguocultural peculiarities of some phraseological units.

Keywords: Linguoculturology, linguoculture, mentality, cultural phenomenon, cultural factor, comparative linguoculturology,

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Each nation has its own national traditions. That is, every nation has its own national traditions and customs. In this sense, everyone is associated with a particular culture, language, history, and literature that reflects that nationality. It is well known that language is not only a social phenomenon, but also an integral part of culture. Today, economic, political, cultural and scientific relations between peoples, nations, countries, international cultural communicative processes in the field of linguistics, the relationship between languages and the culture of language and the national identity of language is leading to the emergence of a new field - linguoculturology, which has a separate direction and subject. As a result, by the end of the twentieth century, a new branch of linguistics, linguoculturology, aimed at studying the problems of language and culture, developed rapidly.

Linguoculturology is a separate field of study that combines language and culture, the phenomena that reflect the interdependence of "language and culture", its formation and development. It is a generalization between the sciences of culture and linguistics, which deals with the interaction and interdependence of language and culture, the formation of this connection and its reflection as a whole system outside language and language. is engaged in learning. On the one hand, linguoculturology studies the role of humanity in the cultural language factor, and on the other hand, it studies the role of man in the language factor. Linguoculturology is relatively close to cultural studies and linguistics in terms of its object of study, but its content can be said to be different in its approach to the object of study. Its limited status is that it studies the national and cultural specific rules of the organization of speech in connection with the expression and expression of folk culture in the language, language mentality, nationality, language psyche, and the language itself of the nation's culture. identifies and studies specific national language features.

Currently, linguoculturology is one of the most developed areas in the world, in particular, Russian and Uzbek linguistics, and a number of textbooks have been created in this regard. Linguists admit that the most famous of them is V.A. It is a study guide created by Maslova. This textbook describes the methods, object and subject, directions in the field of linguoculturology, examples of linguoculturological analysis of a particular language unit [1. 208].

A number of works in this direction are being carried out in Uzbek linguistics. For example, A.Nurmonov's "Linguoculturological direction in the Uzbek language", N.Mahmudov's "In search of ways to perfect language" N.Sayidrahimova's articles "Some comments on the scientific basis of linguoculturology", "Components of linguoculturology", D.Khudoyberganova's hymnography on "Atropocentric study of the text" can be noted. In this work, the essence, subject and object of the science of linguocultural studies are studied.

Linguocultures include words, phraseological units, phrases, sentences, parems, complex syntactic units, texts, etc. that reflect a part of a culture. Linguoculture has a plan of content and expression, the plan of expression consists of the above units, and the plan of content consists of the semantics of those units. Thus, lingvokulturema differs from the concept in that it has its own plan of content and expression, the main task for lingvokulturology is to express the folk culture in a linguistic form. According to him, the concept of "lingvokulturema" is useful for comparative linguistics, "zero language is a cultural fact, an integral part of the culture we inherit, and at the same time a weapon. Folk culture is verbalized through language, which activates the basic concepts of language culture and expresses them in the form of symbols, that is, through words" [4.15].

In Uzbek and Italian, as in all languages, the culture of the nation is reflected in the language combinations and phraseologies. Examples of similar expressions used in these languages are:

Verbs:

Dare la parola a qualcuno - So'z bermoq, gapirtirmoq.

Avere il cuore di fare qualcosa (Avere il coraggio di fare qualcosa) -

Ushbu ibora, Biror narsani bajarishga jasorati bo'lmoq – degan m'noda ishlatiladi.

Dare coraggio - Ruhlantirmoq.

Rubare il cuore a qualcuno (Fare innamorare qualcuno) - Biror kishining yuragini o'g'irlamoq, deb tarjima qilinadi aslida. Ibora, Biror kishini o'ziga rom qilmoq, sevdirmoq ma'nolarini beradi.

Phrases related to animal names:

Lento come una lumaca - Juda sekin

Non si sente volare una mosca - Butunlay jim-jit.

Fare la pecora - Qo'zidek yumshoq bo'lmoq (itoatkor)

Phrases related to color names:

Essere bianco dalla paura - Juda qo'rqmoq.

Essere rosso dalla vergogna - Juda tortinmoq/uyalmoq.

Phrases related to family:

Tenere famiglia - Oilani birlashtirib ushlab turish

Phrases related to the word earth:

Mettere piede a terra - Yerga tushish (ot, arava va boshqalardan)

Phrases related to the word moon:

Luna di miele - Asal oyi

Words and phrases:

Rubare la parola in bocca a qd - Birov aytmoqchi bo'lgan narsani boshqasi ilg'ab oldindan aytib qo'yish.

Uomo di parola - So'zida turadigan/ishonchli odam

Dare parola - So'z/va'da bermoq

Phrases involving body parts:

Dare una mano – Yordam qo'lini cho'zmoq/yordam bermoq.

Alzare le mani - Qo'l ko'tarmoq/urmoq.

Di seconda mano - Ishlatilgan, qo'ldan – qo'lga o'tgan narsa buyum (avtomobil) ga nisbatan ham ishlatiladi.

Chiedere la mano - Qo'lini so'ramoq (*qiz boladan turmushga chiqishini so'ramoq*) ma'nosida ishlatiladi.

Essere in gamba – O'zini o'nqlab olgan, oyoqqa turgan.

Parlare a cuore aperto/col cuore in mano (Parlare con sincerità e fiducia.) – Ochiq ko'ngillik bilan/*Samimiylik bilan gapirish.*

In buone mani – Ishonchli qo'llarda, himoyada bo'lmoq;

In the example of number component expressions:

• **Partire da zero** - So'zma-so'z tarjimada: Noldan jo'namoq – tarzida bo'ladi. Ibora sifatida – *Hech kimni yordamisiz, boshidan/noldan boshlamoq* degan ma'nolarni ifodalaydi.

• **Prendere due piccioni con una fava** - So'zma-so'z tarjimada: Bitta loviya bilan ikkita kaptarni olmoq. Ibora sifatida – *Bir urinish bilan ikki natijaga erishmoq.* ma'nosini ifodalaydi.

• **Dare il cinque** – Mamnunlikni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladigan ishora (ikki kishi orasida qo'l harakati bilan)/ Besh tashlamoq.

• **Fatto trenta, facciamo trentuno** – (Qirqiga chidading, qirqbiriga chida) Biror ishni nihoyasiga yetkazish uchun yana bir ozgina turtki berish.

Here are some examples of the meanings and main features of some of the phrases used in the Italian language - butter, eggs, pepper, salami, bread:

Liscio come l'olio (Andare or filare liscio come l'olio) - Italian is a food-related phrase that translates as slippery on fat. In the original sense, it is used for work that is a problem-free solution. For example: “Com'è andata?” “E' andato/filato tutto liscio come l'olio ” gapini -“Qanday o'tdi?” “Hammasi yaxshi o'tdi/ (silliq) kechdi” we translate as.

Pieno come un uovo - This is an Italian phrase about eggs. Essere pieno come un uovo - when translated, means to be as complete as an egg. The term is often used when one eats too much, which means that a person is unable to eat other foods and has a full stomach. For example: “Vuoi ancora un po' di lasagne?” “No, grazie, sono veramente pieno come un uovo” -“ Yana lazaniya yeysanmi?” Yo'q, rahmat, mening qornim juda to'ydi” we translate as.

Avere le fette di salame sugli occhi - this is another interesting Italian idiom about food. That is, Avere le fette di salame sugli occhi, which translates as salami pieces in your eyes. In fact, this, **agar uning oldida bo'lsa ham, inson haqiqatni ko'ra olmaydi** means. For example, the following sentence: Ma che

hai le fette di salame sugli occhi? Non hai ancora capito che ti mette le corna? - Ko'r bo'lib qoldingizmi? U sizni aldayotganini hali anglamadingizmi? we translate as.

Rosso come un peperone - This is one of the most common Italian phrases about food. Literally translated: essere or diventare rosso come un peperone - means to be red like pepper. Idiomatically, it means that the human face is really red. It can also be called redness or sunburn. Example: Quando ha incontrato Julia ha smesso di parlare ed è **diventato rosso come un peperone** - U Julia bilan uchrashganida, u gapirishni to'xtatdi va qizarib ketdi.

Essere rigido come un baccalà - This is a phrase related to the Italian baccalà fish. Essere rigido come un baccalà, literally **tuzlangan baliq kabi qotib qolish, qotib qolib qarashni** usually means that you are in an awkward situation. Example: Cerca di rilassarti! **Sei rigido come un baccalà!** - Bir oz o'zingni erkin tutishga harakat qil! Yog'ochdek qotib qolding!

Avere le mani di pastafrolla - Idiomatically, it is used to refer to being awkward, rude, or unable to hold something in one's hand. Example: Oggi ho già fatto cadere una tazzina e **un uovo: ho proprio le mani di pastafrolla!** - Bugun men chashka va tuxumni tushirib yubordim: Men juda ham qo'polman!

Essere alla frutta - This is an Italian phrase - it can have different meanings. For example: It can also be used in the sense of power or power exhaustion. Also keep in mind that in Italian, the phrase usually has a negative connotation. Examples: L'anno scolastico è appena iniziato ma io **sono già alla frutta** - Maktab (darslar) endi boshlandi lekin men juda charchadim.

“Buono come il pane” - used in relation to a gentle person.

Language is a mirror of culture, in which not only the real being that surrounds a person, his real living conditions, but also his understanding of the social role of the people, its mentality, national character, lifestyle, customs, set of values and worldview reflected. Language is a cultural treasure, a box, a complex. It preserves cultural values in vocabulary, grammar, phrases, proverbs and sayings, folklore and scientific literature, oral and written speech. Language is a carrier of culture and inherits the national cultural treasure from ancestors to generations. The younger generation will learn the rich cultural experience of their ancestors along with their mother tongue. Language is a tool of culture. it shapes the human personality, the language, through the folk culture. Language is one of the national components of culture. Language, in the first place, helps culture to be both a means of communication and a means of interrupting human communication.

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